

Autoimmune Thyroiditis - As Part of Multiorgan Autoimmune Syndrome(Literature Review)

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Annotation:

The 21st century has been declared the "century of autoimmune diseases", of which there are more than a hundred to date. The natural course of an autoimmune disease is characterized by progression from latent and subclinical stages to clinical and is associated with the presence of specific circulating autoantibodies. During the life of a person with one verified autoimmune disease, there is a high probability of sequential manifestation of other autoimmune pathologies. Every fourth patient with chronic autoimmune thyroiditis develops autoimmune non-thyroidal pathologies, and vice versa, chronic autoimmune thyroiditis is often found among people with non-thyroidal autoimmune diseases. Modern concepts of the pathogenetic mechanisms of development and progression of autoimmune diseases allow us to consider chronic autoimmune thyroiditis as a "signal pathology" in multiorgan autoimmune syndrome.

Keywords: autoimmune thyroid disease; autoimmune polyglandular syndromes; multiorgan autoimmune syndrome; chronic autoimmune thyroiditis; autoimmune diseases

Chronic autoimmune thyroiditis (AIT) was first described by Hashimoto in 1912. Today, several variants of the disease are known. According to morphological features, a hypertrophic form of AIT and an atrophic form of AIT (with signs of fibrosis dominating) are distinguished.[1]. Obviously, there are subtle differences of a genetic and/or pathogenetic nature between the known variants of the disease, but there is also much in common, as a result of which they are quite reasonably combined under one name of autoimmune thyroid disease (AITD) - "chronic autoimmune thyroiditis".

AIT is an HLA-associated disease, but its atrophic and hypertrophic forms are associated with different haplotypes.

In first-degree relatives of patients with AIT, the risk of developing the same disease is 9 times higher than in the general population. The annual incidence of AIT worldwide is 0.3–1.5 cases per 1000 people. The prevalence of AIT is highest in women and reaches 2–11% depending on age. Among adults, 90% of AIT cases are detected in women [2].

Prevalence of AIT

An analysis of literary sources showed that information on the actual incidence of AIT is rather scarce and contradictory. It is not possible to talk about the exact prevalence of AIT itself, since an independent clinical problem is practically not discussed in modern foreign scientific literature; only the most important outcome is assessed - hypothyroidism [2, 3]. However, domestic researchers consider this pathology separately [4]. At the same time, there is quite extensive information on the prevalence of thyroid gland antibody carriage in the population and the frequency of hypothyroidism.

Environmental factors in the development of AIT

In the structure of cause-and-effect relationships in the development of autoimmune thyroid diseases, environmental factors account for 31.8%, being a trigger for the autoimmune process in individuals with a genetic predisposition to the development of AIT [5, 6]. The radiation factor in the development of AIT, which resulted in the release of radionuclides into the environment, was classified as one of the most radioactively contaminated areas. Two radionuclides: short-lived ^{131}I and long-lived ^{137}Cs , made the largest contribution to the population's radiation dose.

Microelement imbalance in autoimmune thyroiditis

An analysis of modern literary data shows that thyroid diseases are associated with an imbalance of a number of microelements (selenium, zinc, copper, chromium, and others) involved in the synthesis of thyroid hormones and affecting iodine metabolism.

Selenium is involved in the conversion of T4 to reversible or active T3 as part of the deiodinase enzyme, and also destroys excess hydrogen peroxide using glutathione peroxidase and thioredoxin reductase, thus maintaining the integrity of thyrocytes. In an experiment with selenium deficiency, the conversion of T4 to T3 was reduced, which proved the role of selenium in the action of thyroid hormones. The action of selenium-dependent deiodinases in tissues is controlled by dietary selenium and has hormonal regulation (it is assumed that it is controlled by thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) [7].

Zinc is also an essential microelement and has a regulatory effect on the synthesis of T4 through the thyroid-binding protein of the nuclear receptor, T3 affects the secretion of TSH, which explains the need for this microelement to implement the biological effect of thyroid hormones. Changes in the level of zinc in daily urine are an indicator for assessing thyroid dysfunction; thus, with its hypofunction, reduced excretion of zinc in urine is revealed.

Copper as a metalloenzyme takes part in the process of converting inorganic iodine into organic compounds, it plays a significant role in ensuring thyroid synthesis. It has been established that copper deficiency contributes to the development of hypothyroidism through a decrease in the activity of iodinase, which is involved in the addition of iodine to tyrosine, as well as through a decrease in the activity of cytochrome oxidase, ceruloplasmin. The dependence of the prevalence of non-toxic goiter on the level of copper in the environment was studied; a decrease in the level of copper in the blood of children with diffuse goiter by 1.3-1.8 times compared to the control was established [10].

A number of microelements are capable of changing the immune response, and many elements are selective in the implementation of their regulatory functions. The possibility of the influence of microelements on immunity, specific points of application of their effects, and the influence on various stages of the metabolism of immunocompetent cells have been established

Violation of immune regulation mechanisms in AIT and hypothyroidism The issue of primary damage to the immune system in AIT continues to be discussed in domestic and foreign literature. Despite this, the hypothesis of the development of autoimmune thyroid diseases proposed by R. Volpe remains relevant today. Thus, autoimmune thyroid pathology occurs as a result of a violation of regulatory processes in the immune system itself, and this violation is associated with a hereditary defect of antigen-specific T-suppressors ($\text{CD3}^+\text{CD8}^+$) and the influence of environmental factors on immunoregulation.[9,10]

Mechanisms of development of AIT

AIT, like other autoimmune diseases, is the result of impaired immunoregulation combined with organic dysfunction, which in turn is a consequence of an antigen-specific attack, supplemented by insufficient suppression (and, consequently, activation) of lymphocytes, whose action is directed at antigens on thyrocytes (target cells), and also in combination with the production of various cytokines that affect target cells from a short distance. Violation of immunological self-tolerance underlies the formation of AIT [2]. Regulatory T-lymphocytes (Treg) play a key role in maintaining self-tolerance and immune homeostasis. They have a suppressive effect on other cells of the immune system, thereby controlling the immune response and suppressing inflammatory reactions by directly suppressing and modulating the function of effector T-cells. In autoimmune processes, in particular in CAIT, a decrease in the number and functional activity of Tregs is observed, as well as the failure of the caspase enzyme, which is involved in ensuring their functionality [3].

It is known that in the pathogenesis of the hypertrophic form of AIT, Th1 (cellular immunity) is involved to a greater extent, and in the pathogenesis of its aB, the following are considered as probable mechanisms underlying the development of AIT:

- disruption of central regulation of tolerance to thyroglobulin (TG), which precedes disruption of tolerance to thyroid peroxidase (TPO) (indicates greater immunogenicity of TG before TPO);
- deficiency and/or dysfunction of regulatory T cells (Treg) that are not involved in the development of autotolerance to the thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) receptor;
- violation of autotolerance to the TSH receptor with the participation of molecules of the major histocompatibility complex, ensuring its polymorphism; • environmental factors and chemical modification of thyroid autoantigens; • molecular mimicry and fetal microchimerism, etc. [8].

It should be noted that thyroid peroxidase is the leading pathogenetically significant autoantigen. In AIT, autoantibodies to TPO are detected in the blood serum of patients in 90–100% of cases. The presence of autoantibodies to TPO is an indicator of aggression of the immune system towards its own body. Unlike others, autoantibodies to TPO are complement-fixing and directly participate in complement-dependent cytotoxicity, which causes an increase in organ-specific autoaggression. A high frequency of autoantibodies to TPO is often observed in non-thyroid diseases: diabetes mellitus (25%), pernicious anemia (52%) and primary biliary cirrhosis (29%) [9].

As noted above, environmental factors (stress, infection, trauma, drugs, smoking, aging) can suppress the functioning of non-specific Ts, thereby aggravating the antigen-specific dysfunction of Ts, and the developing focus of autoimmune damage to thyroid tissue (or any other organ) over time recruits an ever-increasing population of clones of non-specific T-lymphocytes into the affected tissue [8].

The HLA system plays a key role in the processing and presentation of antigens. Antigen presentation by HLA class I and II genes is a fundamental factor in the development of autoimmune diseases, including AIT. This triggers a complex interaction between the antigen present on and produced by target cells, APCs, CD4 helper-inducer T lymphocytes, effector T lymphocytes, and CD8 suppressor (regulatory)/cytotoxic T lymphocytes, and the production of interferon-gamma (IFN- γ) by the activated T lymphocytes, as well as certain cytokine profiles (i.e. Th1 and Th2 cells) and binding molecules (e.g. intercellular adhesion molecules (MMA-1), heat shock proteins, etc.).[6,7]

All of them also play an important role in the coordination of the immune response. For example, the expression of MMA-1 and cell adhesion protein type 1 by thyroid cells, which is not normally observed but is obvious in AIT, enhances lymphocyte activation. Thyroid heat shock protein-

72 is also expressed only by cells affected by an autoimmune attack, but not normally. Such expression may have some immunomodulatory effect in the form of increased immunoglobulin binding. Thyroid cells may also produce some other immunoactive molecules (e.g., prostaglandin E₂, IL-6, and IL-8) as a result of cytokine stimulation or complement attack, which further enhances thyrocyte-immunocyte signaling [5, 6].

And yet, is the presence of a significant internal abnormality in a thyrocyte or in thyroid autoantigens a prerequisite for stimulating the development of AIT? It would seem so, since autoimmunity is a reaction of the immune system to an autoantigen produced as a result of damage to the target tissue or to some other antigen expressed in it. However, in healthy people, lymphocytes have the necessary genes and the ability to produce antithyroid antibodies in response to an increased release of thyroid antigen from inflamed and damaged thyrocytes, but such an excessive release of antigen into the immune system in itself will not lead to AITD. The reaction of the immune system in this case should be and will normally be transient (which is what happens with viral damage to thyroid tissue in subacute thyroiditis or coronavirus infection, when a transient adequate immune response to the release of antigen is observed, but the development of AIT does not occur in the overwhelming majority of patients [7]).

Only in a very limited circle of people (probably those with a genetic predisposition to the development of autoimmune pathologies) a viral or microbial antigen that is similar to an autoantigen (molecular mimicry) is capable of triggering the production of autoantibodies that cross-react with the autoantigen, after which the immune response reacts with the corresponding structures of any autologous cells, including thyrocytes.

The facts of the presence of congenital genetically determined anomalies in the thyrocyte in humans have not been confirmed; many researchers are inclined to believe that the cells of the human thyroid gland affected by the autoimmune process are essentially normal and do not have signs of the original genetic disorders.

Consequently, the occurrence of AIT depends primarily on the presence of initial (genetic) disorders in the immune system. This position is confirmed by the frequent presence of combined autoimmune pathologies in the same person. Moreover, the combination of AIT with other autoimmune pathologies allows us to consider this thyroid disease as a “signal” one, and its detection should alert the clinician to the high probability of the presence or occurrence of new and new autoimmune diseases in the same patient [8].

It is known that damage to two or more endocrine glands provides grounds for the diagnosis of "autoimmune polyglandular syndrome" (APS). However, in addition to damage to the endocrine system organs, APS may also include autoimmune damage to non-endocrine organs. In this regard, in recent years a new classification of APS has been proposed, in which a variant called multiorgan autoimmune syndrome (APS/MAS-3) is increasingly distinguished [9].

As a result, depending on the combinations of autoimmune lesions, four subtypes of APS/MAS-3 are distinguished:

namely:

- subtype A - is characterized by AITD in combination with any other autoimmune endocrine disease, with the exception of 1-CNF and hypoparathyroidism;

- subtype B includes ATG and autoimmune diseases of the gastrointestinal tract (thyrogastric syndrome);

- subtype C is a combination of autoimmune damage to the skin, nervous system or blood with ATG;

- subtype D is a combination of AITD and any autoimmune rheumatic disease. Within this subtype, its incomplete form is distinguished (the presence of AITD and antibodies characteristic of rheumatic diseases, or vice versa - the presence of carriage of antithyroid antibodies and manifest autoimmune rheumatic disease).

Approximately 1/3 of women and 1/4 of men with clinical, subclinical or potential autoimmune diseases are predisposed to develop other autoimmune pathologies, and APS/MAS-3 is the most common APS worldwide [24]. Importantly, genetic predisposition to APS/MAS-3 may be present in more than one family member, and different HLA class II alleles have been correlated with APS/MAS-3 depending on the associated autoimmune diseases. Other genes implicated include those encoding lymphoid tyrosine phosphatase and cytotoxic T-lymphocyte-associated antigen-4 [7].

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